

METAPHOR, MEANING AND ENVIRONMENTAL DISCOURSE IN HELON HABILA'S *OIL ON WATER*

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Abstract

Metaphor functions as a central cognitive and discursive mechanism through which *Oil on Water* conceptualises environmental degradation and its devastating consequences for both the ecosystem and people. This study investigates the metaphorical construction of nature in Helon Habila's *Oil on Water* through the analytical lens of Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory. While existing scholarship has largely examined the novel from political, cultural, and ecocritical perspectives, limited attention has been paid to how metaphor functions as a cognitive and discursive resource for environmental meaning-making. Drawing on twenty purposively selected metaphorical expressions from the text, the study identifies and classifies conceptual metaphors of nature and analyses how they structure representations of ecological degradation and human suffering in the Niger Delta. The findings reveal that natural elements such as water, oil, and landscape are systematically mapped onto source domains of bodily injury, disease, death, and violence, thereby conceptualising the environment as a wounded and violated body. These metaphorical mappings frame ecological destruction as lived trauma and expose the entanglement of environmental crisis with displacement, social disintegration, and Petro-industrial exploitation, and by so doing the study demonstrates that Conceptual Metaphor Theory can be applied in a discourse-sensitive manner to illuminate the ideological and pragmatic functions of metaphor in ecological narratives.

Keywords: Conceptual Metaphor Theory, eco-linguistics, environmental degradation, metaphor of nature, Niger Delta.

Introduction

In recent decades, environmental degradation in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria has attracted sustained national and international concern. Crude oil exploration by multinational corporations has resulted in recurrent oil spills, gas flaring, loss of biodiversity, and the extensive destruction of natural landscapes, with profound consequences for the socio-economic and cultural lives of local communities. As a form of social practice and “mimesis of action” (Aristotle, trans. 1987), literature has responded to these ecological crises by representing, interrogating, and foregrounding the environmental damage occasioned by extractive activities. Among contemporary Nigerian writers who engage with these concerns, Helon Habila stands out, particularly through his novel *Oil on Water* (2010), which narrates the environmental devastation and human suffering associated with oil extraction in the Niger Delta.

Oil on Water narrates the journey of two journalists, Rufus and Zaq, who travel through the Niger Delta in search of Isabel Floode, a British woman kidnapped by militants. Their journey exposes them to polluted rivers, devastated villages, and violent encounters involving soldiers, oil workers, and local insurgents. Through a series of encounters and flashbacks, the novel reveals the cumulative effects of oil exploitation on both the physical environment and the psychological well-being of the region’s inhabitants. Central to this narrative is Habila’s sustained use of metaphors of nature, which function as linguistic and cognitive resources for exposing ecological destruction, critiquing exploitative human–nature relationships, and articulating an emerging environmental consciousness.

Scholarly engagement with ecological concerns in literary and non-literary texts has increasingly drawn on insights from ecolinguistics, a field that emerged in the 1990s as an extension of critical discourse analysis. Ecolinguistics examines how language shapes human relationships with the natural world and how particular linguistic choices promote or undermine sustainable ways of living (Stibbe, 2015). According to Fill and Mühlhäusler (2001), ecolinguistics represents “a new linguistic paradigm that explores the interaction between language and the ecosystem” (p. 4). Within this paradigm, language is viewed not merely as a neutral medium of representation but as a powerful semiotic resource through which ecological realities are constructed, evaluated, and contested.

One linguistic resource that has received particular attention within ecolinguistic and cognitive linguistic scholarship is metaphor, due to its central role in shaping perception, thought, and social action (Deignan, 2005; Kövecses, 2010; Gibbs,

2011). Metaphor is commonly understood as a figure of speech in which one concept is understood in terms of another that is not literally related to it (Wearing, 2014; Wilson, 2011; 2006; Lakoff & Johnson, 2008;). For instance, conceptualising the Earth as a “mother” frames nature as caring, nurturing, and deserving of protection. From a cognitive perspective, metaphors are not merely stylistic embellishments but fundamental mechanisms through which abstract and complex experiences, such as environmental degradation are conceptualised and made meaningful (Black, 1962; Lakoff ,980; 1982; Dennis, 2014). In environmental discourse, metaphors may either reinforce exploitative attitudes towards nature or promote ecological awareness and ethical responsibility.

In this study, metaphors of nature refer to metaphorical expressions used to represent natural elements such as rivers, oil, animals, forests, and landscapes in ways that foreground ecological meanings. These metaphors extend beyond aesthetic or ornamental functions to serve as discursive tools through which readers interpret the emotional, ideological, and political dimensions of human–environment relations (Johnson, 1987; Cartson & Wearing,2011; Gibbs,2013). In *Oil on Water*, for example, water is not merely a physical substance but is often metaphorically construed as a site of danger, contamination, and loss. Through such metaphorical constructions, the novel invites readers to apprehend the depth of ecological destruction and the corruption that underpins it.

Although existing studies have examined *Oil on Water* from political, cultural, and ecocritical perspectives (Asika, 2021; Ebd-Elwahab, 2022; Ogungbemi, 2023), relatively little attention has been paid to the systematic analysis of metaphor, particularly metaphors of nature, as a means of environmental meaning-making in the novel. This gap is significant because metaphor plays a central role in structuring ecological understanding and in mediating between textual representation and socio-environmental reality. Previous studies have not sufficiently explored how metaphorical language operates at a cognitive and discursive level to construct ecological meanings in the narrative.

Addressing this gap, the present study adopts Lakoff and Johnson’s (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory to examine the metaphorical construction of nature in *Oil on Water*. While Conceptual Metaphor Theory is cognitive in orientation, this study applies it in a discourse-sensitive manner, examining how metaphorical mappings function within the socio-cultural and environmental context of the Niger Delta. Specifically, the study explores how metaphors of nature such as those relating to water, oil, animals, and landscapes are used to conceptualise ecological collapse, human suffering, and environmental injustice. The study aims to investigate how metaphorical constructions of nature convey ecological meanings in Habila’s *Oil on Water* using Conceptual Metaphor Theory. The specific objectives are to:

1. identify and classify conceptual metaphors of nature used in the text, and
2. analyse how these metaphors contribute to the novel's representation of ecological crisis

Review of Related Literature

This section interrogates existing literature on Helon Habila's *Oil on Water* with the aim of discussing different approaches used by scholars to explore the text in order to situate the present study properly.

Helon Habila's *Oil on Water* (2010) has attracted considerable critical attention for its representation of environmental degradation and human suffering in Nigeria's oil-rich Niger Delta. A substantial body of scholarship explores the novel's engagement with ecological devastation, political violence, and socio-economic marginalisation. However, despite this growing interest, relatively few studies have systematically examined the novel from the perspective of metaphorical constructions of nature, which is the central concern of the present study. Fernández-Vázquez (2021), in "Into the Heart of Nature: Conradian Echoes in Helon Habila's *Oil on Water*," examines the intertextual relationship between Joseph Conrad's *Heart of Darkness* and *Oil on Water*. His study highlights shared thematic concerns such as moral ambiguity, environmental destruction, and the quest for truth. Fernández-Vázquez (2021) argues that Habila "recontextualises the Conradian tropes to address social and historical concerns related to oil extraction in the Niger Delta" (p. 104), thereby transforming colonial imagery into a postcolonial critique of exploitation. While the study is valuable for its intertextual insights, its primary focus is on colonial legacies and narrative influence rather than on metaphor as a cognitive and discursive resource for ecological meaning-making.

From a linguistic and discourse-analytical perspective, Ogungbemi (2023), in "Literature as Resistance: The Pragmatics of Ecological Advocacy in *Oil on Water*," investigates how language functions as a tool for environmental activism. Drawing on Critical Discourse Analysis and the Appraisal Framework, he analyses evaluative language and rhetorical strategies used to depict ecological destruction and social conflict. Ogungbemi (2023) observes that the novel "shapes the perceived reality of ecological destruction and social conflict" (p. 362), positioning the text as a form of literary militancy. Although his study foregrounds the pragmatic force and affective power of language, it does not engage with conceptual metaphors as cognitive structures underlying ecological representation. The present study differs by focusing specifically on metaphorical constructions of nature.

Similarly, Abd-Elwahab (2022) interprets *Oil on Water* as a critique of environmental injustice resulting from neocolonial exploitation. She contends that “poverty, disease and famine are the first direct consequences of the practices of neocolonialism” (p. 76), demonstrating how oil exploration poisons land and water while undermining subsistence livelihoods. Her analysis centres on the intersection of political betrayal and ecological collapse, portraying the novel as both testimony and protest. While Abd-Elwahab’s study underscores the environmental and humanitarian dimensions of the narrative, it does not address the linguistic mechanisms, particularly metaphor, through which these meanings are constructed.

Edebor (2017), in “*Rape of a Nation: An Eco-critical Reading of Helon Habila’s Oil on Water*,” adopts a sociological ecocritical approach to examine the destructive impact of oil exploitation on the Niger Delta ecosystem. He argues that the novel “makes bare the grim effects of man’s reckless actions on the environment, the society and other living things” (p. 48). Edebor highlights the spiritual and healing value of nature prior to its devastation, drawing attention to moments where nature is represented as a source of restoration, as seen in the Irikefe shrine and the assertion that “the air alone will heal you” (p. 46). Despite these insights, Edebor’s analysis does not interrogate metaphor as a structured system of meaning-making.

Together, Abd-Elwahab (2022) and Edebor (2017) establish *Oil on Water* as a powerful environmental narrative that documents the loss of a once-thriving ecosystem and the resulting human despair. Abd-Elwahab’s warning that “entire nations have deceased by famine and disease” (p. 77) underscores the global implications of environmental abuse, while Edebor advocates an ecocentric worldview that balances development with ecological care. However, both studies prioritise socio-political and ethical concerns over the linguistic construction of ecological meanings, a gap the present study seeks to address through Conceptual Metaphor Theory.

Another strand of scholarship approaches *Oil on Water* as a protest text and a vehicle for ecological advocacy. Egya (2017), in “*Literary Militancy and Helon Habila’s Oil on Water*,” conceptualises the novel as a “belligerent discourse of resistance” against multinational oil companies, the Nigerian military, and local militant groups. He interprets the text as an act of eco-literary activism designed to mobilise both local and global consciousness. While Egya’s study foregrounds resistance and activism, it does not examine how metaphor operates linguistically to sustain this resistance.

Asika (2021), in “*Oily Tears of the Niger Delta: Perspectives on Helon Habila’s Oil on Water*,” examines the politics of oil and media representation in the novel. He argues that Habila’s depiction of competing interests among oil corporations, government forces, militants, and local communities constitutes a significant

literary intervention. Although Asika acknowledges the novel's activist and documentary functions, his analysis remains largely sociological and does not explore metaphorical meaning-making.

Feldner (2018), in "Representing the Neocolonial Destruction of the Niger Delta: Helon Habila's *Oil on Water*," situates the novel within petrocultural discourse, emphasising its critique of neocolonial exploitation under globalisation. He focuses on narrative structure and the journalist-narrator's perspective, viewing the novel as literary witness to ecological and social trauma. Feldner's study, however, prioritises narrative form over linguistic metaphor.

A more metaphor-sensitive reading is offered by Pirzadeh (2021), who examines the symbolic and material roles of water in the novel. She reconceptualises water as an active agent of resistance rather than a passive victim of petroculturalism, arguing that the novel resists neoliberal logic by personifying ecological elements. While Pirzadeh's study aligns with the present research in recognising metaphorical meaning, it is limited in scope to water alone and does not employ Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory. Consequently, it does not account for the broader network of nature-related metaphors that collectively construct ecological consciousness in the novel.

In summary, existing scholarship on *Oil on Water* has explored the novel from ecocritical, sociopolitical, activist, and symbolic perspectives. Studies by Ogungbemi (2023), Feldner (2018), and Abd-Elwahab (2022) foreground ecological destruction and environmental injustice, while critics such as Egya (2017) and Asika (2021) emphasise resistance and eco-activism. Other scholars, including Pirzadeh (2021) and Fernández-Vázquez (2021), attend to symbolic and intertextual dimensions of nature. However, despite these important contributions, there remains a significant gap in the systematic analysis of metaphor as a cognitive and discursive mechanism for constructing ecological meanings. The present study addresses this gap by applying Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory to examine how metaphors of nature in *Oil on Water* shape ecological awareness and ideological understandings of the human–nature relationship.

Theoretical Framework

This study used Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) as its guiding theoretical framework. Conceptual metaphor theory provides a way to understand how metaphor functions as a linguistic structure that reflects human thought. Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT), introduced in their *Metaphors We Live By*, changed the way scholars understand metaphor. Instead of conceptualising metaphors as just creative or poetic expressions, Lakoff and Johnson argue that metaphors are central to everyday thought, speech and even action. According to CMT, metaphors structure human

thought, perception, and communication by mapping familiar concepts, known as source domains, onto more abstract or complex ideas, called target domains. This framework allows for systematic investigation of how language shapes understanding, enabling scholars to examine not only what is said, but how it organises knowledge, directs attention, and conveys ideological meaning. In this perspective, metaphors are not random expressions; rather, they are coherent cognitive structures that reveal underlying conceptual systems operating beneath conscious awareness (Lakoff & Johnson 1980).

A key principle of CMT is that metaphors both highlight and obscure aspects of the target concept. For instance, the metaphor *argument is war* emphasises conflict, attack, and victory, while downplaying cooperation, negotiation, and mutual understanding. Such selective representation demonstrates how metaphors are culturally and socially situated, reflecting values, norms, and shared experiences within a given context. Lakoff and Johnson (1980) further categorize metaphors into structural, orientational, and ontological types. Structural metaphors map one domain onto another, as in *time is money* or *argument is war*. Orientational metaphors organize concepts spatially, such as *happy is up* and *sad is down*, drawing on embodied experience. Ontological metaphors conceptualize abstract phenomena as objects or substances, providing them with definable properties, exemplified in expressions like *inflation is eating our savings* or *the mind is a machine*. These distinctions are essential in literary analysis, as they reveal how language mediates perception, shapes emotional responses, and frames interpretation.

Another central aspect of Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory is systematicity, that is, the idea that metaphorical concepts are not random or isolated, but organised and interconnected in a coherent system. Since, "metaphorical concept is systematic, the language we use to talk about that aspect of the concept is [also] systematic" (Lakoff and Johnson's 1980). It means that when people conceptualise something metaphorically, such as argument is war or time is money, their associated linguistic expressions are consistently structured according to that metaphor. In the case of argument is war, the systematicity explains why people commonly say things like "he attacked every weak point in my argument" or "I demolished his claims". They are not isolated expressions but part of a larger, coherent conceptual metaphor where war is used as the source domain to understand and structure the target domain of argument. This consistency between conceptual metaphor and everyday language demonstrates how metaphor organises not just people's thoughts but also their communication in regular and patterned ways.

Within the context of Helon Habila's *Oil on Water*, CMT offers a powerful tool for understanding how the novel constructs ecological meaning through metaphors of

nature. Rivers, forests, animals, and polluted landscapes serve as target domains, often framed through source domains drawn from human experience, cultural knowledge, or socially salient concepts. Such metaphorical mappings structure readers' comprehension of environmental degradation, human suffering, and socio-political issues in the Niger Delta, while simultaneously foregrounding certain aspects of ecological crisis and obscuring others.

The application of the tenets of CMT, to the analysis of the novel makes explicit how Habila's language organises experience, conveys ideological critique, and cultivates ecological awareness. This equally links metaphor to discourse, cognition, and culture because metaphors are not only cognitive tools but also discursive resources that influence interpretation, guide evaluative judgments, and shape responses to social and environmental realities. In this way, Lakoff and Johnson's framework provides a robust and versatile lens for examining the cognitive, linguistic, and ideological construction of ecological meaning, demonstrating that metaphors of nature in Habila's novel are central to understanding both the narrative and its socio-environmental critique.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative research design; using textual analysis to examine the metaphorical construction of nature in Helon Habila's *Oil on Water*. This approach was used because the study explores meaning-making, cognitive conceptualization, and socio-environmental critique through language, rather than establishing statistical relationships. The focus was on the textual and linguistic patterns within the novel that allows a detailed analysis of how metaphor shapes readers' understanding of ecological crises. The data source for the study is the complete text of Habila's *Oil on Water* (2010). The novel was chosen because it explicitly addresses environmental degradation, human suffering, and the socio-political impact of oil exploration in the Niger Delta, and as such offers a rich material for metaphorical and conceptual analysis. Data selection and sampling involved a purposive approach. Passages depicting natural elements such as rivers, forests, animals, and landscapes were identified as potential metaphoric expressions of ecological meaning. Twenty textual instances that foregrounded environmental realities, human-nature relationships, or socio-ecological commentary were included for analysis. This purposive selection ensures that the analysis focuses on instances where metaphors of nature are most salient in conveying ecological critique and ideological meaning.

Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) used as the analytical framework, provided a systematic method for identifying conceptual metaphors, where a source domain structures the understanding of a target domain. In this study, the target domain is environmental phenomena or ecological

conditions, while the source domain comprises culturally familiar or experientially grounded concepts such as war, disease, contamination, or wealth. The application of CMT to the analysis of the data intends to bring to the fore how metaphors of nature in the novel both structure cognitive understanding and encode ideological stances regarding human interaction with the environment.

The analytical procedure followed three main steps. First, the text was carefully read to identify passages containing metaphorical references to natural elements. Second, each metaphor was categorized according to its type—structural, orientational, or ontological—following Lakoff and Johnson's typology. Third, each metaphor was analysed in terms of its conceptual mapping, semantic function, and socio-environmental significance, in order to highlight how each frames ecological issues, directs attention to particular aspects of environmental crisis, and reveals cultural or ideological assumptions. The analysis also considered how metaphors may simultaneously highlight certain features of ecological reality while concealing others, in line with CMT principles.

Data

The data extracted from the novel is presented below:

1. "A snake, twisting and fast and slippery, poisonous" (p. 35)
2. "An old jute rope, frayed and wobbly and breaking into jagged, feathery ends" (p. 35)
3. "An arrow, straight and unerring, taking us on its tip for miles and miles" (p. 35)
4. Oil is "tight like a hangman's noose around the neck of whatever life-form lay underneath" (p. 42)
5. Oil is "thick, viscous, the colour of bitumen, contained in the transparent bottle of the river" (p. 42)
6. The "oil-soaked earth" is described as a "suppurating wound" (p. 43)
7. a mere trick of light, vaporous and shape-shifting, appearing and disappearing behind the fog" (p. 47)
8. Vegetation "suffocated by a film of oil, each blade covered with blotches like the liver spots on a smoker's hands" (p. 43)
9. Gnarled, hanging roots that grew out of the water like proboscises gasping for air" (p. 37)
10. Pipelines "flying in all directions, sprouting from the evil-smelling, oil-fecund earth" (p. 39)

11. "Ghost that has risen to claim its own" (p. 42)
12. Gas flares and pipelines stand" as a place where "farms once thrived" (p. 39)
13. "Square concrete platform dominated the village centre like some sacrificial altar" (p. 55)
14. "Community of ghosts" (p. 58)
15. "Diseased veins on the back of an old shriveled hand" (p. 148)
16. "The water turned red. Blood; it was blood" (p. 131)
17. "We are mere wanderers without a home" (p. 41)
18. No fish for river, nothing" (37)
19. It pollutes, corrodes, or corrupts many things it touches" (p. 83)
20. we watched the flares shake in the wind but always regrouping to shine again" (p. 56)

Data Analysis

Following the identification and presentation of the metaphors in the previous section, this section undertakes an analysis of the data in accordance with the research objectives guided by the dictates of Lakoff and Johnson's conceptual metaphors (CMs) theory. Helon Habila's *Oil on Water* is rich in the strategic use of conceptual metaphors of nature, which map familiar, concrete domains (source domains) onto abstract environmental realities (target domains). The analysis started with the identification of both the target and source domains of each metaphor followed by their classification into: structural, ontological, or orientational metaphors, in line with Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) and the ecological/ideological significance of each. Table below summarises the conceptual mappings:

S/N	Excerpt	Source Domain	Target Domain	Metaphor Type	Ecological/Ideological Significance
1	"A snake, twisting and fast and slippery, poisonous" (p. 35)	Dangerous animal	Pollution	Structural	Frames pollution as dangerous and unpredictable, evoking caution and moral awareness about ecological hazards

2	"An old jute rope, frayed and wobbly and breaking into jagged, feathery ends" (p. 35)	Fragile object/rope	Environmental/human vulnerability	Ontological	Highlights fragility and decay in both ecosystem and human life
3	"An arrow, straight and unerring, taking us on its tip for miles and miles" (p. 35)	Weapon/projectile	Spread of environmental degradation	Structural	Inevitability and force of ecological harm, linking human activity to unstoppable environmental impact
4	"Oil is tight like a hangman's noose around the neck of whatever life-form lay underneath" (p. 42)	Execution/death	Oil suffocating life	Ontological	Oil is framed as lethal, emphasising moral and ecological consequences of pollution
5	Oil is "thick, viscous, the colour of bitumen, contained in the transparent bottle of the river" (p. 42)	Human artefact/material	Polluted river	Ontological	Depicts oil as contaminating and invasive, merging natural and human made realities
6	The "oil-soaked earth" is described as a "suppurating wound" (p. 43)	Human body injury	Polluted land/soil	Ontological	Humanises the environment, dramatizes ecological pain and anthropogenic destruction
7	a mere trick of light, vaporous and shape-shifting, appearing and disappearing behind the fog" (p. 47)	Illusion/ghostly effect	Environmental instability	Orientalational	Unpredictability of ecological conditions and human disorientation in degraded landscapes
8	Vegetation "suffocated by a film of oil, each	Diseased human body	Polluted vegetation	Ontological	The interconnectedness between human and

	blade covered with blotches like the liver spots on a smoker's hands" (p. 43)				natural suffering with tangible ecological consequences
9	"gnarled, hanging roots that grew out of the water like proboscises gasping for air" (p. 37)	Animal/respiratory organ	Struggling vegetation	Ontological	Highlights plant struggles and ecological disruption foregrounding survival challenges in polluted environment
10	Pipelines "flying in all directions, sprouting from the evil-smelling, oil-fecund earth" (p. 39)	Living organism/plant growth	Industrial infrastructure	Structural	Frames industry as intrusive and unnatural, symbolising destructive human-nature relationships
11	"Ghost that has risen to claim its own" (p. 42)	Supernatural being	Consequences of environmental destruction	Ontological/Orientational	Personifies ecological consequences as morally vengeful
12	"Gas flares and pipelines stand" as a place where "farms once thrived" (p. 39)	Monument	Lost farmland	Ontological	Contrasts past ecological productivity with industrial intrusion, emphasising socio-environmental loss
13	"Square concrete platform dominated the village centre like some sacrificial altar" (p. 55)	Religious altar	Industrial installation	Structural	Frames infrastructure as imposing and destructive, highlighting environmental sacrifice

14	"Community of ghosts" (p. 58)	Spirits/deceased	Displaced people/degraded environment	Ontological	Connects environmental degradation to human displacement and social trauma
15	"Diseased veins on the back of an old shrivelled hand" (p. 148)	Diseased human body	Environmental degradation/suffering	Ontological	Reinforces parallel suffering of humans and environment, demanding accountability
16	"The water turned red. Blood; it was blood" (p. 131)	Human body/injury	River/pollution	Ontological	Evokes empathy and highlights the violence of environmental contamination
17	"We are mere wanderers without a home" (p. 41)	Human displacement	Environmental loss/degraded ecosystem	Structural	Frames ecological destruction as existential and social displacement
18	"No fish for river, nothing" (37)	Absence/emptiness	Collapsed aquatic ecosystem	Ontological	Conveys the tangible consequences of environmental harm on livelihoods and ecosystem
19	it pollutes, corrodes, or corrupts many things it touches" (p. 83)	Contaminant/poison	Oil/environmental impact	Structural	Pollution is framed as morally and physically corruptive, linking human action to ecological degradation
20	"we watched the flares shake in the wind but always regrouping to shine again" (p. 56)	Resilient entity/ military unit	Industrial activity/oil flares	Structural	Suggests persistent ecological disruption, emphasising inescapable human impact on the environment

Classification of the metaphors

Structural metaphors occur when one concept is organised in terms of another. Lakoff and Johnson (1980) defined them as "cases where one concept is metaphorically structured in terms of another" (p. 15). In the novel, structural metaphors are used to map characteristics of familiar source domains into the structure of the Niger Delta environment and the industrial structures imposed upon it. The mappings are relevant as they help the readers understand the setting as a site of conflict. The river as a snake, an old jute rope, and an arrow (Habila, 2010, p. 35) illustrates this category. The target domain (river) borrows structure from animals, objects and weapons. The readers can grasp the mappings of the Delta's waterway as alive, fragile and threatening. The conceptual metaphor as shown in the Table (S/N 1) portrays the river as something dangerous. A similar structural pattern appears when industry is described as vegetation: pipelines are said to be sprouting from the evil-smelling, oil-fecund earth (Habila, 2010, p. 39). Here the mechanical world of oil extraction is portrayed in the light of the natural growth of plants. It creates a bitter irony in which technology imitates the life it destroys.

In addition, the structure describes the river as "an arrow, straight and unerring" (S/N 3). It casts the natural flow as an instrument of fixed danger and linear trajectory and suggests that the journey is predetermined by external, hostile forces. The conceptual metaphor identified in the Table (S/N 10) imposes the structure of natural growth into the mechanical, destructive infrastructure of oil extraction. This structural inversion highlights a malignant fertility, which means that the earth's ability to generate life is replaced by its ability to cause toxicity. The metaphor maps the structure of military conflict such as violence, loss, and devastation into the economic sphere and positions the oil operation as an act of calculated destruction against indigenous livelihoods. Finally, the metaphor in the Table (S/N 13) frames the community using the ritualistic structure of offering and loss. It signifies that the Delta communities are destined to be sacrificed due to economic forces. The metaphor in serial number 17 extends this structure to the human dimension by mapping social displacement as homelessness. The metaphor portrays the inhabitants as perpetual victims of dislocation caused by oil exploitation. It maps moral and spiritual decay onto physical contamination. Thus, oil is conceptualised as a corruptive social force, not as an industrial substance. These structural metaphors reveal the way Habila represents the systematic breakdown of nature, morality, and community under the dominance of petro-capitalism.

Ontological metaphors, on the other hand, treat abstract processes or non-human elements as entities with physical or human qualities. In the words of Lakoff and Johnson (1980), they are "ways of viewing events, activities, emotions, ideas, etc., as entities and substances" (p. 26). Ontological metaphors are fundamental to the novel's eco-critical approach. They enable abstract environmental threats and non-

discrete entities (like oil and pollution) to be treated as concrete entities. This mechanism changes environmental threats into tangible villains and victims. Hence, it compels an emotional and moral response from the reader with regards to the nature of the ecological injury. A dominant ontological metaphor in the novel is the personification of the land and its resources. It depicts nature as a suffering victim. This is most evident in the Table (S/N 8) and (S/N 9). By referring to the land and roots as anthropomorphic victims afflicted by illness and suffocation, the abstract environmental injury is turned into tangible, bio-physical trauma. The river too is ontologically referred to as a predator as seen in the Table (S/N 1). It is a reflection of the hostility and danger of journeying in toxic water. In addition, the formless substance of oil is given three distinct tangible identities that tag it as a killer. Excerpt 4 makes the oil synonymous with execution.

Excerpt 6 grounds the pollution in the ontology of medical trauma. It equates contamination with a festering infection. Also, excerpt 5 describes the unnatural containment of the thick, opaque pollutant within the transparent vessel of the river. Furthermore, the trauma is extended to the industrial and social spheres by bounding them as spectral figures. Excerpt 14 ontologically defines the inhabitants as entities that are present physically but politically and economically absent. On the other hand, excerpt 11 elevates the industrial process to a supernatural spirit. The metaphor in the excerpt 15 continues this bodily framing. The landscape is mapped into the aging and weakened human body. It makes the earth's degradation synonymous with human decay. Similarly, excerpt 16 personifies the river as a bleeding body; this image fuses human and environmental pain. It portrays the river as a victim as well as a witness of violence. Finally, the metaphor in the excerpt 18 assigns lifelessness to the river. It transforms it into a dead organism. In summary, the ontological metaphors reconstitute nature as a sentient, vulnerable being. In this way, it humanises ecological loss to evoke empathy and moral urgency in the reader.

Oriental metaphors draw on spatial experience (up, down, centre, edge) to express emotional or moral states. They are employed to organise abstract concepts using spatial relations. The metaphors rely on physical experience (such as movement, direction, and visibility) to structure abstract thought. The conceptual metaphor in excerpt 7 describes the scenery as "vapourous and shape-shifting, appearing and disappearing behind the fog" (Habla, 2010, p. 47). It is an example of orientational device. Here, the difficulty of spatial orientation (the inability to fix the landscape in space) is mapped into conceptual uncertainty and the difficulty of attaining truth and suggest that the ideological and political ambiguity of the Delta conflict is obscured by the environment which makes certainty an elusive goal.

Similarly, in excerpt 11, the vertical resilience of the flares signifies the persistence of oppressive power. Despite natural forces like wind (symbol of resistance), the destructive fire of capitalism endures and reasserts dominance. This mapping constructs an orientational schema where *rising* equals destruction and oppression instead of vitality. While the spatial orientation of up is linked to positive concepts (up is good, up is power), the flare's "rising" (upward movement) is inverted by its association with a destructive ghost. This re-orientation establishes up is danger, and makes the metaphor a symbolic representation of oppressive power that dominates the horizontal plane of communal existence

Metaphoric Representation of the Ecological Crisis

The preceding analysis established the nature of Habila's use of metaphors across the categories of Structural, Ontological, and Orientational CMs. Moving beyond classification, this section explores the way the identified metaphors function to construct a coherent and devastating, narrative of ecological crisis.

Habila's *Oil on Water* gives a detailed picture of the ecological breakdown of the Niger Delta. One of the clearest ecological crises the novel explores is the pollution of aquatic life and the collapse of livelihoods that depend on it. The novel repeatedly narrates about the dead or silent waterways. For example, in a meeting called by Chief Malabo, their major problem is that their rivers were already polluted and useless for fishing, and the land grew only gas flares and pipelines (Habla, 2010, p. 29). The statement is stark. Rivers that were once prominent to the diet and trade of the community can no longer provide food, and farmland has been replaced by industrial hardware. What should sustain life now produces only smoke and metal. This metaphor of rivers without fish signals the breakdown of an entire economy and the disappearance of the cultural practices (net-casting, communal fish markets, river festivals) that depended on a living waterway. The novel increases this sense of devastation by a story of older violence that lingers in the landscape. A priest recalls that during a forgotten war:

The blood of the dead ran in the rivers, and the water was so saturated with blood that the fishes died, and the dead bodies of warriors floated for miles on the river, until they were snagged on mangrove roots on the banks, or got stuck in the muddy swamps, half in and half out of the water. The land was so polluted that even the water in the wells turned red (Habla, 2010, p. 91).

Here, the river itself is a witness to massacre that carry corpses and turn wells to red colour. Though the event is historical, it mirrors the representation oil disaster.

A related crisis is chronic contamination of shorelines, wells and soil. The novel gives frequent, precise images of plants and ground covered by oil. It narrates that the patch of grass growing by the water was suffocated by a film of oil, each blade

covered with blotches like the liver spots on a smoker's hands (Habila, 2010, 6). The narration sees pollution as a lasting stain. The film and the blotches speak to slow, accumulative harm. Crops fail, wells taste of petrol and land that once yielded food becomes unfit for planting. Habila contrasts a memory of abundance with the present ruin to show how oil pollution reaches even the deepest soil and wells. An elder recalls that once upon a time they lived in paradise fishing and hunting and farming and watching their children growing up before them, happy (Habila, 2010, p. 28). The past village is described as self-sufficient, its families joined by rivers, farmland and shared labour. Now that paradise is gone: oil leaks have seeped into the ground, the streams that fed their farms carry residue, and the wells that once gave clear drinking water taste of crude.

Furthermore, oil itself is depicted as an active, killing force rather than a neutral resource. Rufus imagines the weight of the oil tight like a hangmans noose around the neck of whatever life-form lay underneath (Habila, 2010, p. 56). The comparison to a noose is stark and deliberate. It makes clear that spillages and leakages act like strangulation for fish, shellfish and other life that depends on clean water. Thus, the novel portrayed oil not as a mere commodity but as a direct agent of death. Practically, this metaphoric representation explains the long-term decline of fisheries and the collapse of small-scale economies. Politically, it points a finger at the systems that put extraction above care for ecosystems.

Air pollution and the steady burning of hydrocarbon waste are another ecological crises in the novel. Habila notes that the gas flares that always burned in the distance" are part of the landscape (Habila, 2010, p. 28), and later he records how inland, the smoke rose like a tornado into the sky, high over the savaged, seared trees (Habila, 2010, 63). The metaphors used here record two kinds of harm. First, the constant flaring and smoke worsen local air quality which raises rates of coughs, breathing problems and other health complaints. Second, the light and noise of continuous flares disturb the natural rhythm of night and day, and they erase the ordinary soundscape of birds and insects. The result is a damaged atmosphere and a lived environment that is always under industrial pressure.

Land use change and the spread of infrastructure deepen the damage to soil and ecology. The novel describes the invaded landscape in practical terms, as when pipes and rigs appear to take over open ground. Rufus remarks on a place "sprouting from the evil-smelling, oil-fecund earth (Habila, 2010, p. 26). The language suggests that the earth now bears industrial hardware instead of crops or forest. The physical alteration matters for drainage, for mangrove health and for the way water moves through the system. It also breaks traditional patterns of farming and foraging. Once the land is cut by pipelines and dotted with wells, the chances of any ecological recovery fall unless deliberate restoration takes place.

Violence and militarisation compound ecological harm and make recovery harder. The novel links attacks, raids and the presence of armed forces to scenes of destruction and death. On one journey Rufus and company see human remains among the wreckage when once we saw a human arm severed at the elbow bobbing away from us, its fingers opening and closing, beckoning (Habla, 2010, p. 25). The same social violence that produces bodies in the water also prevents people from returning to their ruined fields or from safely fishing the creeks. Military patrols, pipeline protection and the actions of armed groups all make it dangerous to mount restoration projects or to sustain local livelihoods. Ecological crisis and armed conflict form a loop that deepens the harms. In another passage, “*we are mere wanderers without a home*” (p. 41). This expresses the displacement crisis that follows ecological ruin. It shows the way people become refugees in their own land. Also, the novel captures the corruption of the ecosystem with the observation that oil “*pollutes, corrodes, or corrupts many things it touches*” (p. 83). This line has literal and metaphorical functions. Literally, oil erodes soil fertility and corrodes metal and wood. Metaphorically, it corrupts human morals and governance. Environmental degradation denotes a moral and social sickness.

Finally, the novel depicts the cultural and psychological effects of long-term environmental loss. Empty settlements and abandoned sites recur in Rufus’s journey. Habla writes that a square concrete platform dominated the village center like “*some sacrificial altar*” (Habla, 2010, p. 5), and that whole villages feel like “*a community of ghosts*” (Habla, 2010, p. 6). These metaphors represent the erosion of social memory, ritual life and local authority. When people are scattered, when rites tied to place cannot be performed, and when landmarks are industrialised, the social fabric that supported environmental stewardship weakens.

Discussion of Findings

This study set out to examine how nature is metaphorically constructed in Helon Habla’s *Oil on Water* through the lens of Conceptual Metaphor Theory, with particular attention to the relationship between language, ecological crisis, and socio-cultural meaning. The analysis demonstrates that metaphor in the novel is not merely ornamental but operates as a cognitive, ideological, and pragmatic resource through which environmental degradation and its human consequences are conceptualized, evaluated, and contested.

First, the findings show that Habla relies on systematic conceptual mappings in which nature and ecological processes (target domain) are structured through source domains of disease, death, violence, sacrifice, and the supernatural. These mappings are not isolated stylistic flourishes but recurrent patterns that instantiate deeper conceptual metaphors such as nature is a wounded body and pollution is a killing force. For instance, the description of the “oil-soaked earth” as a

“*suppurating wound*” (p. 43) maps bodily infection (source domain) onto the landscape (target domain), foregrounding pain, decay, and vulnerability. Similarly, the image of vegetation “*suffocated by a film of oil*” with blotches “*like the liver spots on a smoker’s hands*” (p. 43) draws on the source domain of chronic illness to conceptualize environmental damage as slow, degenerative, and irreversible. Through these bodily mappings, ecological degradation is framed as a form of physical injury rather than an abstract environmental process.

Second, the analysis reveals that metaphor functions pragmatically to position readers morally and emotionally by activating shared embodied experiences. A clear example is the metaphor in which oil is described as being “*tight like a hangman’s noose around the neck of whatever life-form lay underneath*” (p. 42). Here, execution (source domain) structures oil pollution (target domain), pragmatically attributing agency, intentionality, and moral culpability. This metaphor narrows interpretive possibilities by framing oil extraction not as accidental harm but as lethal violence. In CMT terms, the familiarity of the source domain—execution—guides readers toward a particular evaluative stance, aligning them with the victims of ecological violence and against its perpetrators.

From a sociolinguistic point of view, these metaphors also encode collective ecological experience and local knowledge in the Niger Delta. Utterances such as “*no fish for river, nothing*” (p. 37) compress ecological collapse into everyday vernacular, mapping environmental loss onto lived deprivation. Similarly, the statement “*we are mere wanderers without a home*” (p. 41) conceptualizes displacement (target domain) through the source domain of homelessness and rootlessness, highlighting the social consequences of environmental degradation. The depiction of villages as a “*community of ghosts*” (p. 58) extends this mapping further, drawing on the supernatural as a source domain to represent social erasure and loss of identity. These metaphors index shared social meanings and reflect how ecological damage is experienced linguistically within affected communities.

Moreover, the novel persistently personifies industrial structures, producing an ideological reversal in which industry is animated while nature is rendered passive and wounded. Pipelines are described as “*flying in all directions, sprouting from the evil-smelling, oil-fecund earth*” (p. 39), and gas flares are said to “*shake in the wind but always regrouping to shine again*” (p. 56). In these cases, growth, movement, and resilience (source domains associated with life) are mapped onto industrial objects (target domain), while rivers are imagined as “*blood*” (p. 131) and roots as “*proboscises gasping for air*” (p. 37). Within CMT, this contrast reveals how metaphor can naturalize industrial dominance while depicting nature as weakened and dependent. At the same time, Habila’s exaggerated personification exposes this imbalance, prompting readers to question the assumed inevitability of industrial expansion.

Importantly, the study demonstrates that metaphor in *Oil on Water* performs an ecological consciousness-raising function. By repeatedly mapping environmental degradation onto domains associated with pain, death, and moral transgression—such as wounds, execution, and blood—the novel cultivates an ecolinguistic awareness that is both cognitive and affective. The river turning “red... blood” (p. 131) does not merely describe pollution; it conceptually equates ecological harm with human mortality. Such mappings encourage readers to interpret environmental destruction as unjust and ethically troubling, reinforcing the link between language, perception, and environmental values.

Finally, the findings extend Conceptual Metaphor Theory beyond cognitive description to critical socio-pragmatic interpretation. While CMT explains how metaphors structure thought, this study shows how these structures are mobilised within specific socio-historical conditions to negotiate power, responsibility, and resistance. In *Oil on Water*, metaphors of disease, death, and haunting function simultaneously as cognitive mappings and as discursive acts that contest ecological exploitation and social injustice. In this sense, Habila’s metaphorical construction of nature operates not only at the level of cognition but also as a sociolinguistic intervention in debates about environmental ethics and human accountability.

Conclusion

The study successfully achieves its aim and objectives by analysing the way Habila’s *Oil on Water* employs metaphor and language to represent ecological issues in the Niger Delta. The application of Lakoff and Johnson’s (1980) conceptual metaphor theory indicates that the novel depicts the environment as active and relational. Hence, environmental degradation attracts social, cultural and economic consequences. The study confirms that Habila uses metaphors like the metaphors of rivers, vegetation, oil and human settlements to represent deep ecological ideas.

The key findings reveal that the novel represents ecological harm in multiple dimensions. Rivers, plants, and soil are shown as suffering entities, while oil and industrial activity are depicted as agents of destruction. Waterways are polluted, crops are smothered, and air quality is damaged which lead to the collapse of livelihoods and local economies. Metaphors and descriptive language also convey the cultural and psychological effects of environmental loss, as abandoned villages and disrupted social rituals reflect social decay. In addition, language exposes ecological consciousness, and links environmental care with justice, responsibility and resistance to exploitation.

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